

SOCIO-PHILOSOPHICAL ANALYSIS OF SOCIAL LIFE AND GLOBALIZATION PROCESSES

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Abstract: This article analyzes the processes of social life and globalization, the role of information in the globalization of the economy, the introduction of information and communication and computer technologies and their transition to a path of rapid development, which will bring great changes to our society, the formation of a general information society in the world, ensuring the rapid and high-quality circulation of information, which has become the main criterion for the development and prosperity of the country.

Keywords: economy, globalization, information, information and communication, computer technologies, information society, information systems, telecommunications.

Introduction. The social-reformist ideas and communist utopia that prevailed until the nineties of the 20th century did not justify themselves. On the eve of the 21st century, the world experienced, on the one hand, ideological instability, and on the other hand, ideological indifference. In particular, if ideological instability is manifested in the absence of ideas that can unite entire peoples in the world, then ideological indifference is expressed in the indifference of people to the idea that occupies their consciousness and activities.

Materials and methods

We have shown that the main object of influence of religious extremism, nationalism and many similar ideas remains the countries that have gained their independence. Because the main goal of geopolitics is to strengthen its position in other regions and to take these regions under its influence, and the various political forces in the world include young sovereign states in their interests, promoting the ideas we have mentioned in order to weaken their independence.

Results and discussion

He is using various ideological, religious, and ideological means to undermine the socio-economic, cultural, and educational ties that have formed in the region, to provoke conflict between peoples and nations, and to create foci of tension. Ideological pressure on independent states is carried out as information warfare, psychological warfare, technological warfare, the true purpose of which is to instill in the nation a system of alien lifestyles and values, to mislead it from its chosen path, to introduce its own technology, and ultimately to take it under its influence and pursue a colonial policy.[1] These tools can be conditionally attributed to three areas:

Informed war. In the context of expanded information transmission capabilities, information warfare has dangerous consequences. On the eve of the nineties, only in the United States did 1850 periodicals focus on ideological goals. To date, the introduction of satellite antennas into everyday life and the development of the internet system have accelerated the possibilities of information transmission.

Psychological warfare. It is a desire to instill in the people of independent states the incorrectness of their chosen path, to justify the fact that social shocks await them in the end. All this is done in order to lower the spirit of the nation, to turn it back from its chosen path.

Technological warfare. To attract the attention of independent states, attempts are being made to promote their own economic, social, and information technologies. The goal of this is to create a market for the implementation of these technologies, which, along with new technologies, will allow for the assimilation and export of one's own development model.

In such conditions, conditions are being created for the development and spread of such inhuman ideas as religious extremism, nationalism, which primarily affects countries that have just gained their independence. These ideas are disseminated and promoted to realize the geopolitical goals of various political forces.[3]

The process of globalization has fundamentally changed the world's ideological landscape, creating new goals and directions of geopolitics. As a result, on the one hand, methods and techniques for instilling various ideas in people's minds were perfected, and on the other hand, the ability to protect citizens from the influence of inhuman ideas decreased. In the current situation, the collapse of the Soviet Union and the socio-political events that took place in other regions of the world pose a particularly serious threat to the security of countries that have gained independence.[4] Therefore, to gain comprehensive information about the nature of ideological pressure on countries that have gained independence, it becomes necessary to study the ideological image of the present time.

Indeed, the ideological image of the modern era is characterized by a diversity of ideas and the intensity of ideological struggle. In the context of ideological instability and ideological indifference, these factors threaten the security of Uzbekistan. It is precisely for this reason that it is necessary to understand that the ideological landscape that has emerged today is a legitimate product of the development of human society in the 20th century, and it is necessary to understand that its stability and security can only be ensured by forming an idea that expresses the dreams and interests of the nation in the context of an intensified ideological struggle.

Ideology is a superstructural phenomenon that is shaped by socio-economic and political events. Therefore, the acceleration of globalization in the 20th century and the beginning of the formation of global civilization changed the nature of world ideologies. The lack of a powerful ideology to replace them, and the changing geopolitical goals, further exacerbated the negative impact of these ideas.[5] In such conditions, only a nation that has clearly defined its goals, well-aware of its needs and interests, has its own beliefs, in short, has formed its own national idea, will preserve its future and determine its prospects.

Conculion

Therefore, the following conclusions can be drawn: globalization creates conditions for national, religious, and cultural ties between people on a global scale; through the exchange of scientific and technical information, technologies, and scientific and technological achievements, it opens up unprecedented opportunities for human development on an international scale; large opportunities and benefits inherent in globalization are widely distributed among countries and people, and the results of scientific and technological progress are reaching countries that are not their creators. For example, the vast capabilities

of the Internet can be used in all countries; on the basis of global technological capabilities, opportunities arise to improve human development and eradicate poverty.

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